

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES OF COMPLEX FORMATION BETWEEN
MOLYBDIC AND TARTARIC ACIDS. PART IV. PHOTOCHEMICAL
REDUCTION OF MOLYBDIC ACID IN PRESENCE OF *d*-TAR-
TARIC ACID AND THE INFLUENCE OF REDUCTION ON
OPTICAL ROTATION

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The kinetics of the photochemical reduction of molybdic acid in presence of *d*-tartaric acid have been studied and the quantum efficiency of the process has been measured. The dependence of the rate of reduction on the concentrations of both complex and uncombined molybdic acid, its variation with change of $\mu\pi$ of the system and the appearance of different shades of the reduced solutions, have been explained. Evidence from rotation measurements of the reduced solutions indicates that the complex does not break into its components by reduction.

Benrath (*Z. wiss. Photochem.*, 1917, 16, 253) observed blue coloration after short exposure to sun light, in an aqueous solution of ammonium molybdate in presence of either ethyl or methyl alcohol and stated that the complex formed and not neutral molybdate, was reduced, the colour being due to the blue oxide Mo_2O_3 . Courtius (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1923, 33, 1773) observed that uranyl tartrate was stable in the dark but rapidly reduced in sunlight to a dull yellow compound in the absence of air. Dumanakii and Diatschkovsky (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 60, 1053) exposed to light a solution of sodium tungstate in tartaric acid and attributed the blue colour to the formation of a reduced colloidal complex. Bhattacharyya and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 510) have studied the photo-reduction of ammonium molybdate by tartaric, mandelic and lactic acids in the ultraviolet (366μ) and found that the reduction velocity varied with the colour of the reduction product, the velocity being maximum when the end-product was pale yellow and diminishing when green products were formed.

Ghosh and collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 495 *et seq.*) have made extensive investigations on the photo-reduction of various photo-active sols by various reducing agents like alcohols and organic acids; the mechanism of those reactions have been explained on the assumption that active centres are created on the colloid surface by absorption of light which start the reactions. The object of the present investigation is to throw further light on the process.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The reaction cell (4 cm. $\times$ 4 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.), made of plane glass fused into one another with a glass stopper at the top, was placed inside a double jacketted metal box and its temperature was kept constant by circulating water; the light coming from a quartz-mercury arc lamp was condensed with a suitable quartz lens and from the emergent rays the spectral region 366μ was isolated with the help of a "Schott and Gen ultra-violet filter No. 312". The arc lamp was supplied with a steady current at 220 volt and the distance of the reaction cell from the light source was kept constant.

Reagents.— B. D. H.'s pure *d*-tartaric acid was further purified by recrystallisation from redistilled water. Pure NaOH solution free from carbonate was used. The preparation of molybdic acid sol from ammonium molybdate and HCl was described in a previous communication. Redistilled water was always used for making solutions.

Measurement of Reaction Velocity.—This was determined by pipetting out 5 c. c. of the reaction mixture into a glass stoppered conical flask containing dilute H_2SO_4 and titrated with $0.6688 \times 10^{-2} N$ - $KMnO_4$ solution from a micro-burette. It is to be noted here that the end-point of this titration is very fugitive, although the $KMnO_4$ solution cannot appreciably react with tartaric acid solution when present separately at the same concentration as present in its mixture. The titration was carried out as quickly as possible and the first appearance of the pink colour was taken as the end-point.

The reduction of molybdic acid (MoO_3) in presence of tartaric acid (H_2T) did not appear to take place in the dark within 6 hours, but on long standing (15 days) in the dark, indications of slight reduction were observed from the faint blue colour. The reduction rate in the dark was therefore extremely slow but on short exposure to ultra-violet light the reduction started immediately.

The rate of reductions by radiation of 366μ of mixtures at different concentrations of both molybdic and tartaric acids has been studied here and also of similar mixtures at different p_H brought about by the addition of a suitable quantity of NaOH solution. The p_H was measured with glass electrode as before. The velocity of reaction expressed as dx/dt =zero-molecular velocity constant=changes in concentration of 5 c.c. of the reaction mixture per minute in terms of volume of $0.6688 \times 10^{-2} N$ $KMnO_4$ solution. Previous to exposure to light, the reaction mixture in the cell was freed from dissolved oxygen by bubbling pure nitrogen for sometime in the dark and then fixing and sealing the stopper with wax. The velocity of reduction of molybdic acid sol with varying concentration of tartaric acid at 25° is shown below.

TABLE IA

Reduction by full radiation from Hg-arc lamp, the cell being placed at a distance of 15 cm.

Conc. of MoO_3	Conc. of H_2T	p_H	dx/dt	Colour of the product.
$2.36 \times 10^{-2} M$	$0.57 \times 10^{-2} M$	2.32	73.10×10^{-4}	Deep blue
"	1.14	2.12	130.0	"
"	2.36	2.08	150.0	Pale blue
"	4.69	1.90	133.0	Pale yellow with greenish tinge
"	9.37	1.87	73.0	Pale yellow

TABLE IB

Reduction by ultraviolet light— 366μ .

Conc. of MoO_3	Conc. of H_2T	p_H	dx/dt	$ko \times 10^{11}$	$I_{366} \times 10^{11}$	ν	Colour of the product.
$2.6 \times 10^{-2} M$	$0.65 \times 10^{-2} M$	2.29	33.3×10^{-4}	7.42	35.95	0.20	Deep blue
"	1.30	2.09	46.6	10.39	34.40	0.30	"
"	2.60	1.99	50.0	11.15	28.96	0.39	Pale blue
"	5.21	1.82	33.3	7.42	19.24	0.38	Pale yellow with greenish tinge
"	10.43	1.75	26.6	5.93	13.60	0.43	Pale yellow

In the above table and also in the following, the quantum efficiency ν ($= \frac{k}{I_{\text{abs}}}$) of the process of photo-reduction has been calculated thus: it has been assumed that one mole of KMnO_4 reproduces 5 moles of reduced molybdic acid to the original oxidant stage according to the equation $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{MoO}_3$, and thus the zero molecular velocity constant is recalculated and given in the table as k_0 , which expresses the number of g. mols. of molybdic acid transformed per second in a unit cell of 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. I_{abs} represents the intensity of radiation (366 $\mu\mu$) absorbed in Einsteins per sq. cm. per sec. by a column of solution of 1 cm. thickness.

It will be noticed that the velocity of reduction is maximum when MoO_3 and H_2T are equimolecular in concentration, and it decreases on both sides of this ratio. The colour of the reduction product changes from deep blue when $[\text{MoO}_3] > [\text{H}_2\text{T}]$ to pale yellow when $[\text{MoO}_3] < [\text{H}_2\text{T}]$.

The effect of p_n on the reduction rate of different mixture of MoO_3 and H_2T has been studied and the results are given in Table II below.

TABLE II

Compn. of the mixture in $M \times 10^2$.	p_n .	$dx/dt \times 10^4$.	$k_0 \times 10^{11}$.	$I_{\text{abs}} \times 10^{11}$.	ν .
2.60 MoO_3 0.65 H_2T	2.20	33.3	7.42	35.95	0.20
"	3.46	26.6	5.93	33.43	0.18
"	6.14	5.0	1.11	18.27	0.06
"	7.50	1.0	0.22	4.86	0.05
2.60 MoO_3 1.30 H_2T	2.09	46.6	10.39	34.40	0.30
"	3.99	36.6	8.16	31.49	0.41
"	6.18	5.0	1.11	21.82	0.05
"	7.83	0.5	0.11	4.47	0.02
2.60 MoO_3 5.21 H_2T	1.82	33.3	7.42	19.24	0.39
"	2.56	26.3	5.80	18.65	0.31
"	5.87	8.0	1.92	12.82	0.15
"	7.21	0.9	0.21	4.47	0.04
2.60 MoO_3 10.43 H_2T	1.75	26.6	5.93	13.80	0.43
"	2.71	20.7	4.62	11.66	0.40
"	6.15	6.0	1.47	10.50	0.14
"	7.75	1.0	0.22	4.08	0.05

It will be noticed in the above table that p_n values of the systems have an appreciable influence on the rate of reduction and it is remarkable that above p_n 5.0, the values of dx/dt rapidly diminish. It is also to be noted that the quantum efficiency of the process is much less than unity in all cases.

The influence of reduction on the optical rotatory power of the complex molybdo-tartaric acid solution is represented in Table III.

TABLE III

Compn. of the the mixtures in $M \times 10^3$.	*Amount of reduction.	Observed rotations at wave-lengths											
		690 $\mu\mu$			578 $\mu\mu$			436 $\mu\mu$					
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)			
2.36 MoO ₃ 0.67 H ₂ T	2.01	+0.10	(-)	+0.09	+0.13	(-)	+0.13	+0.17	(-)	+0.16	+0.34	(-)	+0.32
2.36 MoO ₃ 1.14 H ₂ T	2.61	+0.021	(-)	+0.20	+0.26	(-)	+0.25	+0.21	(-)	+0.30	+0.54	(-)	+0.50
2.36 MoO ₃ 2.36 H ₂ T	5.40	+0.38	+0.36	+0.36	+0.48	+0.44	+0.43	+0.55	+0.50	+0.49	+1.05	+1.05	+0.96
2.36 MoO ₃ 4.68 H ₂ T	3.84	+0.55	+0.54	+0.56	+0.71	+0.70	+0.68	+0.79	+0.77	+0.75	+1.57	+1.56	+1.54
2.36 MoO ₃ 9.37 H ₂ T	2.10	+0.71	+0.72	+0.70	+0.90	+0.87	+0.87	+1.01	+0.97	+0.95	+1.90	+1.80	+1.81

* "Amount of reduction" is expressed in terms of a.c. of 0.6688N-KMnO₄ solution per 10 c.c. of the reduced solution.

Suffix (1) represents rotation values before reduction.

.. (2) .. " after reduction.

.. (3) .. " after titration of the reduced mixture with KMnO₄ solution to reproduce the original oxidant.

The rotation values corresponding to the mark (-) could not be measured due to the intense blue colour of the solution; but after titration with KMnO₄ solution it was possible to measure them because the reduced solution became colourless at the end-point. The observed rotation values are corrected for dilution caused by the addition of the titre and noted in the table. It will be seen that there is no appreciable increase or decrease of rotation values caused by the reduction.

DISCUSSION

Addition of H₂T to pure MoO₃ sol exposed to ultraviolet makes it very susceptible towards reduction. The cause of this reduction superficially indicated by some is due to complex formation. But Ghosh and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) assumed the formation of active centres on colloid surface. Following the observations of Jander and others (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 194, 413) that aggregates of different compositions of MoO₃ are formed at different p_n of the sol, they explained the observed different reduction velocity at different p_n on the assumption that micelles of different compositions differed in their photo-activity.

It has been observed in our case that reduction takes place in a system where there is no free or uncombined H₂T present (*i.e.* when $[MoO_3] \cong 4 [H_2T]$) according to our observation in Part I, Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 351) and also where there is no colloidal particles present, all the solutes being apparently present in true solution (*i.e.*, when $[H_2T] \cong 4 [MoO_3]$) according to our observations in Part III, *ibid.*, 1946, 23, 257). The reaction is obviously going through some other mechanisms and we have advanced here a plausible conception by which all the observed facts can be explained.

The application of the concept of "stabilisation of valences by co-ordination" can explain all the observed facts. It is well known that the oxidation-reduction potential of ions is greatly altered through the formation of complex ions of varying stability. This often leads to a stabilisation of valency of the element in question in higher or lower states of oxidation. From among many such known examples may be cited the addition of pyridine or thiocyanate ions into nickel (ous) chloride and cobalt (ous) chloride, both of which form strongly co-ordination compounds and this increases the ease with which nickel and cobalt ions are reduced (Lingane and Kerlinger, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1941, 13, 77). Probably molybdic acid is similarly stabilised at lower state of valency by forming a co-ordination compound with H_2T and hence it becomes susceptible towards reduction, slowly in the dark and rapidly in the ultraviolet, by capturing electrons from the surroundings or making some other suitable rearrangement within the molecule itself.

The course of reduction probably proceeds thus : The complex molecule $H_2(MoO_3T, H_2O)$ and its ions are first reduced but free molybdic acid, when present in the mixture, takes away the acquired electron from the complex and is itself reduced probably to Mo_2O_3 or some other product which has a blue colour. The complex thus, acts like a catalyst transferring its acquired electron to its neighbour so long as unreduced free MoO_3 is present. After that the reduction of the complex itself goes on and its rate of reduction becomes slower than the above process.

Accordingly the velocity of reduction depends on the concentration of both free MoO_3 and the complex in a mixture and an optimum proportional concentration of the two to show maximum reaction velocity is attained when MoO_3 and H_2T are present in equimolecular proportion (Table I)

The colour of the reduction product from blue to yellow (Table I) can be accounted thus : The colour of reduced MoO_3 is blue and that of the complex is pale yellow. When the $[MoO_3]$ is much greater than $[H_2T]$, the colour of reduced MoO_3 predominates, but when $[H_2T]$ is preponderating, the colour of the reduced complex predominates and in intermediate stages the observed colour is the mixture of the two extremes.

The variation of reduction velocity with p_n can be explained on the assumption that the unionised molecule $H_2(MoO_3T, H_2O)$ is more easily reduced than its ions and so reduction velocity decreases with increase of p_n . But above p_n 5.0, the rapid drop in velocity to a very low figure (Table II) is due to the fact that the complex begins to dissociate into its components above p_n 4.2 (as shown in part II, Biswas, *ibid.*, 1946, 23, 249) when the concentration of the complex rapidly decreases and the component molybdate ion as itself has little tendency to reduction.

The application of the electronic theory of valency also reflects the relative instability of the complex as depicted before.

Sidgwick ("The Electronic Theory of Valency", p. 163, Oxford University Press, London, 1927) has suggested that the stable valency groups are formed when the "effective atomic number" of the central atom is equal to that of an inert gas. On this basis the marked stability of $Mo(CN)_6^{IV}$ present in aqueous solution of the complex

